

**Carbon Transition Risk
and
Climate Laws in United States**

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Abstract

In this study, we investigate the influence of U.S. climate legislation on the relationship between carbon emissions of S&P 500 firms and their stock returns from 2010 to 2019. We use reported total carbon emissions as our primary measure for carbon transition risk and rely on a novel public database on climate laws to construct a climate law index. Our findings primarily indicate that investors price carbon transition risk based on emission levels rather than emission intensity. Specifically, an increase of one standard deviation in total emissions is associated with a 2.8% decrease in stock returns. However, the persistent negative relationship between carbon emissions and stock returns post-climate law implementation is not evident. Further investigations show that high climate change awareness amplifies the negative effect on “brown” stocks post-climate law introduction, suggesting a shift in investor sentiment towards greater climate risk perception. Nonetheless, our findings suggest that these effects might diminish over time without continuous strengthening of climate legislation.

Keywords: Carbon transition risk, Stock returns, Carbon emissions, Climate laws, Climate Awareness, Risk premia.

JEL Classification: K32, O16, O51, Q54, Q58

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[..] Climate change is happening now and to all of us. Every week brings a new example of climate-related devastation. No country or community is immune.

A. Guterres, United Nations Secretary General.

1 Introduction

Climate change stands out as one of the most pressing challenges of our era. The rising global temperatures have amplified awareness because of the diverse threats they pose to all aspects of society. The increasing frequency of natural disasters, combined with the evident consequences of climate change, heightens public attention to environmental issues and concern about climate-related risks (El Ouadghiri et al., 2021; Ardia et al., 2022; Guo et al., 2020). Consequently, countries across the globe are faced with the challenging endeavor of implementing policies to limit the temperature rise. Recognizing this undeniable reality, it becomes imperative for policymakers to adopt swift measures to mitigate the climate emergency. For instance, when the Paris Agreement was ratified in 2015, all 196 participating countries pledged to deliver their nationally determined contributions (NDCs). These commitments primarily detail their strategies for curbing greenhouse gas emissions (GHGs) to meet the objectives set by the Paris Agreement. More recently, the U.S. House of Representatives has approved the Inflation Reduction Act of 2022, allocating roughly \$370 billion towards clean energy and climate measures in the upcoming decade. This act is set to cut the country’s carbon emissions by around 40% by 2030, fulfilling the U.S.’s international commitments. Upon its enactment, this law will signify the leading global carbon emitter’s dedicated effort to tackle the climate challenge head-on.

With the rising concerns over climate risks and their importance in decision-making, an important question emerges: how do stock market investors respond to governmental environmental actions, particularly the introduction of environmental regulations? For instance, Monasterolo and De Angelis (2020) reveal that investors demanded higher returns for holding carbon-intensive assets, but this was notably evident only post the Paris Agreement. In a similar vein, a recent study by Bolton and Kacperczyk (2023) highlights a significant shift in the carbon premium before and after the enactment of the Paris Agreement, noting a considerable and statistically significant premium following the agreement. More related to our study, Bolton and Kacperczyk (2021b) find that domestic policy tightening is a driver of the relationship between stock returns and firm-level carbon emissions.

In this study, we aim to investigate how the U.S climate legislation influences the relationship between stock returns and S&P500 companies’ carbon emissions during the period from 2010 to 2019. To achieve this, we first design a climate law indicator. This indicator draws its data from the publicly accessible “Climate Change Laws around the World” database, which is a comprehensive collection of national laws specifically aimed at reducing greenhouse gas emissions. To represent the exposure to carbon transition risk, we use companies’ carbon emissions as a primary measure of their environmental stance. In our baseline analysis, we place emphasis on the reported carbon emissions of the more carbon-intensive or “brown” companies, specifically their total CO₂ emissions (Scope 1 + Scope 2). We also consider carbon emissions intensity (total reported carbon emissions normalized by sales) to avoid the potential bias associated with firm size that might result from unscaled carbon emissions, as highlighted by studies such as (Bolton and Kacperczyk, 2021b; Bauer et al., 2022; Aswani et al., 2023). Using a generalized panel Two-Way Fixed Effects (TWFE) model, our analysis involves regressing the monthly stock returns of S&P500 companies on our climate law indicator, the reported carbon emissions, and most importantly, the interaction term of these two factors.

Our baseline empirical results indicate an apparent premium linked to price adjustments prior to climate law implementation, suggesting green companies might outperform less eco-friendly ones when climate concerns rise. Investors have shifted their focus, valuing total emissions over just emissions intensity, indicating a change in the perception of environmental risks in the market. Specifically, an increase of one standard deviation in reported total emissions is associated with a decrease of 2.8% in stock returns, on average. Upon the introduction of climate legislation, there's evidence that investors may adopt a wait-and-see approach, but also penalize companies with larger carbon footprints. The effects are notably visible in the months after these laws come into play, but less so when looking at their long-term impact. "The focus is on total carbon emissions since they offer a more transparent view of a company's environmental footprint, potentially putting high-emitting companies at greater risk of climate regulation.

Furthermore, using the climate awareness time-series indicator from [Engle et al. \(2020\)](#) derived from media coverage on climate change, further investigations suggest that during periods of high climate awareness, the negative impact of carbon emissions on stock returns becomes more pronounced two months after the introduction of a climate law, continuing for nearly a year. However, 12 months post-legislation, this effect diminishes, indicating that persistent legislation impacts might require continuous reinforcement.

Our study intersects two distinct areas of focus within the climate finance literature. The first of these is concerned with how climate risks affect asset price valuations, specifically investigating whether carbon emissions are incorporated into stock prices. While empirical research on this subject has been gaining ground only recently ([Campiglio et al., 2019](#)), the existing studies show varied conclusions based on the proxies used for assessing climate risk and the methodologies applied, such as asset pricing or panel regression frameworks ([Bauer et al., 2022](#); [Aswani et al., 2023](#)), or the kind of financial assets considered ([Giglio et al., 2021](#))¹.

Focusing on the cross-section of stock returns, most of empirical studies develop a "carbon portfolio" taking a long or short position on a firm-level climate risk exposure and investigate whether it is priced on the market. A seminal work in this area is by [Görgen et al. \(2020\)](#), who define a "brown" minus "green" (BMG) factor by calculating the returns between companies with higher and lower carbon scores. Their work did not reveal a significant global carbon premium during the 2010-2017 period, meaning that companies with higher carbon footprint levels do not necessarily earn higher returns. [Oestreich and Tsiakas \(2015\)](#) designed a "dirty" minus "clean" portfolio based on emission allowances allocated to German companies participating in the EU Emissions Trading System (ETS) during the 2003-2009 period. Their findings indicate that companies granted more than 1 million emission allowances—essentially the highest emitters included in the "dirty" portfolio—consistently outperformed those that received fewer allowances, which were included in the "clean" portfolio. Similarly, research by [Witkowski et al. \(2021\)](#) corroborated this trend for energy-intensive companies in the EU ETS, but extended the study period to 2003-2012. On the contrary, focusing on European electric utilities, [Bernardini et al. \(2021\)](#) report that an investment strategy on low-carbon companies delivers higher realized returns during post-2012 period, during the years in which the decarbonization process accelerated. In a same vein, [Alessi et al. \(2021\)](#) found a negative carbon premium—lower emitting companies exhibit higher realized returns—for European individual stock returns. Using an innovative metric to gauge firm-level exposure to carbon-associated risks—incorporating both carbon emissions and the quality of environmental disclosures—they found that investors accept lower returns to hold

¹The author provides a comprehensive and general literature review on climate finance.

greener and more transparent stocks. Closer in spirit, [Hsu et al. \(2023\)](#) study focused on the broader environmental impact, specifically analyzing toxic emissions. By using these emissions as a metric for assessing a company’s greenness, they found that an investment strategy favoring companies with high toxic emissions could result in average annual return of 4.42%, termed as a “pollution premium”. Besides, a study by [Bolton and Kacperczyk \(2021b\)](#) found a significant carbon premium, particularly indicating that both the level and changes in carbon emissions have a positive, significant impact on stock returns. One key difference with the previous studies lies in the sample size, the direct use of carbon emissions as a proxy for transition risk by [Bolton and Kacperczyk \(2021b\)](#) instead of carbon scores and the panel regression framework to assess the impact of carbon emissions on stock returns. The study conducted by [Bolton and Kacperczyk \(2021a\)](#) on the US stock market highlighted that companies that have higher carbon emissions tend to have increased realized returns because investors demand compensation (higher risk premia) to hedge this carbon risk. Conversely, [Bauer et al. \(2022\)](#) found that, when assessing companies greenness based on reported carbon emissions, green stocks have outperformed brown stocks in G7 countries over the past ten years.

Nevertheless, given the divergent findings in prior research, a growing subset of the literature on green finance is placing more emphasis on how investors and the general public perceive the impact of climate risk on stock market valuations. Theoretically, [Pástor et al. \(2022\)](#) demonstrate that green companies could outperform their brown counterparts when concerns about climate change increase unexpectedly. This suggests that while brown firms might experience lower realized returns, they could simultaneously exhibit higher expected returns. Such a scenario might arise if the valuation of green assets has seen a spike in recent years due to a shift in investor preferences. For instance, [Bolton and Kacperczyk \(2021b\)](#) suggests that the carbon premium they identified can be attributed, at least in part, to the selective screening undertaken by institutional investors. This screening is performed to curtail the carbon risk within their investment portfolios. Based on textual analysis of major US newspapers, [Ardia et al. \(2022\)](#)² develop a climate news indicator aiming to gauge the environmentally-driven preferences of investors stemming from climate change and found that green stocks outperform brown ones during the days with an unexpected increased in climate change concerns. [Choi et al. \(2020\)](#) found that unexpected local temperature spikes cause investors to reconsider their perceptions of global warming captured by the Google Search Index (GSI). Their result indicates that high carbon-emitting companies tend to face reduced returns during these unusual temperature increases. In the same line, [Guo et al. \(2020\)](#) suggest that environmental concerns play a major role in the response of stock market to environmental policies. Another relevant paper that touches upon the regulatory impacts, especially in the European context is the one from [Busch et al. \(2016\)](#). Their study explores the evolving understanding of sustainable development within financial markets. The authors delve into how stricter environmental regulations, coupled with increased investor and consumer awareness, can affect company valuations and stock performance. However, in a study conducted with institutional investors, [Krueger et al. \(2020\)](#) determined that while these investors are concerned about climate and regulatory risks, such risks aren’t entirely reflected in equity valuations.

Our study builds on a line of research examining the impact of climate legislation on stock returns. Many studies in this field use the event study methodology, focusing on the stock market’s reactions to unexpected climate events, often measured through cumulative abnormal returns as dependant variable. For example, [Hengge et al. \(2023\)](#) explored the EU ETS’s effect on stock returns and found

²In the same line, [Engle et al. \(2020\)](#) introduced a climate news index derived from US newspapers, formulating a portfolio strategy explicitly designed to hedge climate-related risks.

that unexpected rises in carbon prices led to negative returns. Similarly, [Guo et al. \(2020\)](#) noted that stocks of major Chinese polluters reacted more strongly to new environmental policy announcements, highlighting that stricter environmental laws induce more significant stock market reactions. [Borghesi et al. \(2022\)](#) analyzed reactions to green-policy announcements by major European governments in 2020, finding positive returns for both green and brown portfolios, but a stronger positive effect for the green one. [Sautner et al. \(2023\)](#) introduces an innovative metric to evaluate firm-level exposure to climate-related risks deriving from an analysis of the discourse pertaining to climate change among participants in earnings calls³. They found that exposure to regulatory events have a negative impact on stock valuations. Along these lines, [Faccini et al. \(2023\)](#) broke down climate risks into four categories: natural disasters, global warming, international summits, and US climate policy. They document that, notably after 2012, only the climate risk tied to government interventions is reflected in US stock prices and that a firm’s exposure to regulatory shocks is negatively associated with stock valuation.

Our study contributes to the existing literature through two main ways. Firstly, we employ a publicly accessible climate laws database to measure U.S. climate legislation. Secondly, in light of the ongoing debate on transition risk pricing in stock markets, our research brings a nuanced perspective. Besides, we explore the extended effects on stock returns following the introduction of climate laws during the 2010-2019 timeframe instead of focusing solely on notable climate events or environmental news. In doing so, our work not only bridges these two domains of research but also investigates the implications of transition risk pricing in the stock market, specifically in response to U.S. climate actions—a facet that remains underexplored in previous studies.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follow. Section 2 presents our data and especially how we construct the US’ climate law indicator. Section 3 describes our empirical strategy to assess how US climate legislation affects the relationship between stock returns and company-level carbon emissions. Section 4 presents our baseline empirical results. Section 5 provides further investigations on our analysis and Section 6 concludes.

2 Data

This section presents the data used in our empirical study. We outline how we constructed our indicator for US climate initiative laws and the exposure of S&P500 companies to transition risk.

Our final dataset is assembled by combining two primary databases. The climate law database discussed in [subsection 2.1](#) is publicly accessible, while the databases covered in [subsection 2.3](#), [subsection 2.4](#), [subsection 2.5](#) are sourced from Thomson Reuters. In the case of the latter, we employ ISIN as the principal identifier to merge the data. Ultimately, we integrate the CCLW and Thomson Reuters databases, using the monthly date as the key identifier. The database ultimately compiles 17,791 observations spanning the years 2005-2018.

2.1 Climate Change Laws of the World database

The *Climate Change Laws of the World* (CCLW) is issued from the collaboration between The Sabin Center and the Grantham Research Institute on Climate Change and the environment. The database is publicly available that encompasses roughly 2,000 climate policies and laws from 200 countries globally. To date, it stands as one of the most expansive and accessible free resources on climate policy available

³The dataset spans a considerable breadth, encompassing over 10,000 firms across 34 countries within the time frame of 2002 to 2020 and available at: <https://osf.io/fd6jq/#!>.

for download. The database incorporates laws and policies that detail a government’s approach to addressing climate change or are part of its climate strategy. This encompasses overarching climate change laws, as well as laws tailored to specific sectors or issues, and those promoting decarbonization and/or climate resilience. More specifically, it includes laws directly targeting climate change and dedicated climate measures as well as those that inadvertently affect it. It addresses all pertinent measures geared towards diminishing greenhouse gas emissions, including foundational regulations. Only laws and policies of national significance are included⁴. The database adopts a fairly broad definition of climate legislation. This can be divided between legislative acts (those passed by the government), accounting for about 40%, and executive orders (issued by the government), making up roughly 60%. To simplify the analysis, we refer to all these measures as ‘laws’ (Eskander and Fankhauser, 2020).

Our analysis focuses on the United States, and we’re constrained by the accessible data on CO₂ emissions. Originally, we identified 53 climate laws spanning from 1963 to 2023. However, some laws have undergone amendments or are part of the same legislative family. To prevent double-counting of a single law, we’ve excluded these overlapping entries to maintain a unique identifier for each distinct legislative event. As a result, Figure 1 shows the initial count of climate laws included in the database.

Figure 1: Number of US Climate Laws (1963-2023)

Note: The figure represents the number of environmental laws passed in the United States, as recorded in the CCLW database, over the period 1963-2023.

subsection 2.2 illustrates the annual enactment of climate laws in United States. The former climate law was the Clean Air Act, ratified on December 17, 1963. The figure reveals that a mere four climate laws were instituted before the turn of the millennium. Post-1999, there’s a notable uptick in the enactment of climate laws. We observe an increasing trend from 2007, with legislative activity peaking between 2021 and 2023. Over 11 new laws came into effect just since 2021.

2.2 Climate law indicator

This subsection is dedicated to detailing the construction of the US’ climate law indicator.

We aim to investigate the pricing of transition risk in the US stock market following the enactment of climate laws. Initially, we introduce an indicator variable named ‘Law_Event’. This variable is assigned a value of 1 for every time a climate law is enacted during our study period and 0 otherwise, designing to an event study approach. Formally, we denote the following dummy variable as follows:

⁴<https://www.lse.ac.uk/granthaminstitute/climate-change-laws-of-the-world-database/>

$$LAW_t = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{the date the climate legislation was enacted} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Furthermore, our aim is to analyze the reaction of S&P 500 companies post the introduction of these climate laws. To delve deeper into the long-term implications, we establish a dummy variable that assumes a value of one for the specific duration in which we seek to observe the impact. For instance, if we aim to examine the effects one month post-law enactment, the variable is set to “1” for that month. We extend this logic to capture effects for durations of up to 12 months. For clarity and simplicity, consider the following example detailing the construction of our climate law index. Suppose a climate law was enacted in January 2013, marking it as the Law Event. We then structure the climate law index as outlined in [Table 1](#):

Table 1: Climate Law Index

t	0M	1M	2M	3M	4M	5M	6M	7M	8M	9M	10M	11M	12M
01/2013	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
02/2013	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
03/2013	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
04/2013	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
05/2013	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
06/2013	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
07/2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
08/2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1
09/2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1
10/2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1
11/2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1
12/2013	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
01/2014	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1

Note: This table provides an example of the construction of the climate law indicator. Source: Author’s computation.

The primary objective of our study is to understand the response of S&P 500 companies to the introduction of climate laws. Rather than using the traditional event study methodology, which primarily captures immediate market reactions within short windows surrounding an event, we employ a more encompassing approach. We introduce a dummy variable in our baseline specification, where this binary variable is triggered for a specified duration to observe the impact. This approach, unlike the narrow focus of traditional event studies, allows us to delve into both immediate and prolonged effects on stock prices. The aim is not just to measure the immediate repercussions of a specific climate law but to understand the broader, sustained implications of the U.S.’s climate change regulation on stock market valuations over an extended timeframe. This methodology provides depth, minimizes short-term market noise, and captures evolving long-term market sentiments, offering a comprehensive view of the market’s adjustment to climate regulations.

2.3 Measure of CO₂ indicator

To assess companies’ exposure to transition risk, we rely on their carbon emissions, quantified in tons of CO₂ annually. Such a metric has become a standard method in empirical research to proxy a company’s carbon footprint ([Bolton and Kacperczyk, 2021b,a](#)).

However, employing this indicator necessitates a multi-step process. Initially, carbon emissions are classified according to the categories delineated by the Greenhouse Gas Protocol nomenclature⁵, formulated in 2001. Essentially, a company’s greenhouse gas emissions fall into three distinct scopes that define its emission boundaries. Scope 1 covers the company’s direct carbon emissions from its owned or controlled sources. Scope 2 encompasses the indirect emissions arising from the company’s purchased energy consumption. The sum of Scope 1 and Scope 2 forms the Total emissions, while Scope 3 captures emissions from the production units within a company’s supply chain. Our analysis primarily hones in on Total emissions—derived from the sum of Scope 1 and Scope 2—given the challenges and scarcity of data surrounding Scope 3.⁶ We also provide robustness checks using just Scope 1 or 2 emissions.

The **Figure 2** displays the average carbon emissions over our sample period ranging from 2010 to 2019. We observe a general decline during the overall observation period, with emissions dropping to less than half of what they were at the start of the observation period⁷.

Figure 2: Average reported total carbon emissions (in tons)

Note: This figure represents the average carbon emissions measured in tons of CO₂ over the our observation period 2010-2019.

Furthermore, a potential bias emerges when using carbon emissions related to the company’s scale. Companies emitting identical carbon amounts but varying in size might have distinct carbon footprints. (Ilhan et al., 2021) advocate for the carbon intensity approach, which involves dividing a company’s emissions by its sales, as a main metric for assessing carbon emissions’ impact on stock returns. This method of evaluating carbon intensity is a prevalent standard in the field, helping sidestep any size-related biases in our CO₂ measurements.

Lastly, a pertinent concern while using carbon emissions is choosing between reported and estimated emissions. The former restricts the sample size, while the latter could introduce bias. Notably, Aswani et al. (2023); Bauer et al. (2022) highlight significant variations between these two, questioning the dependability of estimated emissions. While more companies are now either mandatorily or voluntarily disclosing their emissions, many still remain non-transparent about their carbon footprint.

⁵For more details, see <https://ghgprotocol.org/>.

⁶Busch et al. (2022) demonstrate that the CO₂ emission intensity consistency (either self-reported by firms or estimated by third parties) among various third-party entities diminishes from Scope 2 to Scope 3.

⁷For our empirical analysis, we express carbon emissions using their natural logarithm. Besides, we winsorize carbon emissions variables at 1% level following (Bolton and Kacperczyk, 2021b,a). Estimation results are provided in **Appendix D** when we release the winsorization at 2.5% level.

Consequently, our main analyses primarily focus on using reported emissions, turning to estimated emissions only for the purpose of conducting robustness tests. Concerning the aforementioned challenges related to using carbon emissions as the primary metric for carbon emissions indicators, our sample selection is restricted. As previously mentioned, there are still companies that do not report their carbon emissions data. To enhance the reliability of our findings and optimize our sample size, we focus on companies listed in the US S&P 500 index. This approach provides us with a strongly-balanced dataset, featuring 437 companies after dropping firms operating in the financial sector and covering the period from January 2010 to December 2019 on a monthly basis. All the carbon emissions data are standardized to ensure clarity in our empirical estimation.

2.4 Dependent variable

Our analysis focuses on US S&P 500 companies listed on the primary US stock exchanges, NYSE and NASDAQ. We limit our consideration to active and primary quotations, excluding companies within the financial sector. Monthly stock returns are calculated using the logarithmic difference of the adjusted closing price:

$$r_{i,t} = \ln(P_{i,t}) - \ln(P_{i,t-1}) \quad (2)$$

where $P_{i,t}$ is the price of stock i at time t ⁸. We have expressed the monthly returns in percentage to simplify interpretation. To mitigate the influence of outliers, we winsorize the returns at the 1% level⁹.

2.5 Control variables

In this subsection, we provide details on the control variables specific to each company within our dataset. These individual characteristics have been conventionally adopted in academic literature to adjust for potential trends or cross-sectional variations that are likely to explain our dependent variable, individual stock returns. Specifically, we consider the following variables: Size; Return on Equity (ROE); Tobin Q; Debt; Book-to-market; Property, Plant, and Equipment; Research and Development expenditures; Sales growth; Momentum; and Investment.

To integrate these variables into our empirical framework, we undertook several transformations. Size is defined as the logarithm of market capitalization.¹⁰ Tobin Q is represented by the logarithm of the market-to-book value ratio. Book-to-market is calculated as the inverse of the lagged market-to-book value. Property, Plant, and Equipment (PPE) variable is the ratio of PPE to total assets. Research and Development expenditures is normalized by dividing the expenditure by total assets. Investment is initially computed as the ratio of total assets to its lagged value; we then determine its difference and represent it in percentage terms. Sales growth is derived from the annual growth rate of net sales. Momentum is captured using a rolling window of monthly stock returns from $t - 12$ to $t - 2$. Through these transformations, we aim to ensure compatibility and consistency in our empirical analysis. [Table A-2 in Appendix A](#) provides descriptive statistics of the control variables¹¹.

⁸Here, P_t is the closing price on the first day of month t .

⁹[Table A-1 in Appendix A](#) provides descriptive statistics of the dependant variable.

¹⁰In robustness checks, we utilize the logarithm of total assets as an alternate measure of company size.

¹¹Tobin Q, Debt, Book-to-market, Sales growth, Momentum, Investment and ROE are winsorized at 1% level to limit the impact of outliers.

3 Empirical methodology

In this section, we describe our identification strategy to assess the impact of carbon emissions on stock returns, conditional upon climate change litigation in the US. Initially, we seek to determine whether this climate risk is priced in following the enactment of climate laws. Following that, we intend to evaluate if carbon emissions influence stock prices, regardless of the climate regulatory landscape.

Given that context, we adopt an empirical approach grounded in a traditional panel framework. Using a generalized Two-way Fixed Effect model (TWFE), we assess the effect of carbon emissions on S&P500 companies conditionally to US’s climate initiatives.

This method is commonly utilized in research to estimate a causal effect from panel data. To enhance our model’s accuracy, we factor in unit and time-based adjustments to account for any unobserved consistent characteristics that could affect the dependent variable. Specifically, we include a variable to balance out any average discrepancies across our sample, ensuring a more accurate representation of the data.

In its former specification, the model takes the following form:

$$r_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \theta_i + \gamma_t + \beta_1 CO2_{i,t-1} + \beta_2 CO2_{i,t-1} \times LAW_t + \sum_{k=3}^K \beta_k X_{k,i,t-1} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (3)$$

The dependant variable $r_{i,t}$ represents the monthly stock returns of US S&P500 companies. $CO2_{i,t}$ indicates the total carbon emissions reported by each company at a specific time, t . In this baseline specification, we consider carbon emissions as a continuous variable. As detailed in [subsection 2.3](#), reported total emissions is used as our main measure of carbon emissions indicator. To mitigate potential endogeneity concerns, we refrain from regressing stock returns on carbon emissions for the same year. Following the approach of [Bauer et al. \(2022\)](#), we lagged the carbon emissions data by one period (equivalent to one year, given that carbon emissions data is available annually). As we focus on reported carbon emissions, it is inferred that companies experience a reporting lag in disclosing their carbon emissions data, implying that such data might not be instantly reflected in stock prices¹². LAW_t refers to climate law indicators discussed in [subsection 2.2](#).

Lastly, $X_{k,i,t}$ is a set of control factors specific to each company, which we detail in the [subsection 2.5](#). In line with established financial literature, we also lagged the control variables by one period. This approach helps prevent look-ahead bias and guarantees that the information was accessible to investors during the relevant stock return period¹³.

Both γ_i and θ_t denote firm-specific and time fixed effects, respectively. These are fundamental features of a TWFE model as explained above, which controls for unobserved characteristics and patterns that vary across units and over time. $\varepsilon_{i,t}$ refer to a normally distributed error term.

We estimate [Equation 3](#) using Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) and report one-way cluster-robust standard errors to account for correlation within firms.

Our interest in estimating this relationship is twofold. Firstly, we aim to discern if the US stock market prices the risk associated with climate change. This is represented by the coefficient β_1 in the [Equation 3](#). More precisely, this coefficient illustrates the average impact of carbon emissions on stock returns when no climate law has been enacted during the observation period, while adjusting for all confounding variables that might affect stock returns. For instance, a positive and significant coefficient implies that, on average, companies with higher emissions in our sample earn higher returns.

¹²We provide in [Appendix C](#) estimation results with no emissions publication lag as [Bolton and Kacperczyk \(2021a\)](#).

¹³All control variables are lagged by one period, except for the sales growth and investment-to-assets variables.

More crucially, our focus is directed towards the coefficient of the interaction term between carbon emissions and our climate law indicators β_2 . This coefficient signifies the effect of carbon emissions on stock returns when a climate law is enacted. The combined impact of these variables sheds light on whether the market adjusts the pricing of transition risk in response to US initiatives aimed at carbon emission reductions. In this way, we expect that β_2 is negative. This implies that after the implementation of climate laws, the influence of carbon emissions on stock returns is likely to be negative.

Given its design, our model might introduce multicollinearity challenges due to the concurrent inclusion of time-invariant dummy variables and time fixed effects. Although the coefficient for the dummy variable isn't a focal point of our analysis¹⁴, we carry out econometric tests to confirm the robustness and appropriateness of our model for the empirical study. Specifically, we aim to determine whether adding our climate law indicator significantly improves the model's ability to explain the relationship between carbon emissions and stock returns. To achieve this, we use the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) (Akaike, 1974) and Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) (Schwarz, 1978), which are widely recognized in academic research for model selection. We first compare the coefficients from the initial model, which doesn't include climate law indicators, to the coefficients of subsequent models. While there's a contradiction between the two information criteria, the AIC criterion suggests that in 90% of the specifications, incorporating our climate laws indicator results in a better fit to the data. This lends further support to the validity of the model we've chosen for our study.

4 Baseline results

In this section, we set forth our principal empirical findings from Equation 3. To begin our discussion, we'll highlight the debate on whether the transition risk is incorporated in stock prices in subsection 4.1.¹⁵ Following that, in subsection 4.2 we explore the potential causal effects of US climate legislation on the relationship between carbon emissions and stock returns.

4.1 Are carbon emissions reflected in stock prices?

In the context of discussing whether transition risk is reflected into stock valuation, Figure 3 presents the coefficient related to our carbon emissions indicator, β_2 .

To be more precise, according to the formulation of our baseline Equation 3, the coefficients in this graph represent the main effect of reported total emissions on stock returns without the climate law¹⁶.

Our analyses consistently show that carbon emissions have a negative impact on stock returns across different specifications. The coefficient is notably negative, statistically significant, and tends to hover around -2.8. This suggests that investors are pricing in the carbon transition risk at the company level. More specifically, this means that in the absence of the climate law (or before its implementation), an increase of one standard deviation in the reported total emissions is associated with a decrease of 2.8% in stock returns, on average. This is particularly true when we use emission levels as the main measure for carbon emissions, although the findings contrast with those reported in Bolton and Kacperczyk

¹⁴We've chosen to exclude the coefficient related to this variable to prevent potential issues with overlapping data effects. At this point, we're keen on understanding how carbon emissions influence stock returns after a climate law is implemented, rather than how a climate law affects stock returns when the average emissions of our observed companies are zero.

¹⁵Corresponding tables are provided in Appendix B.

¹⁶Note that carbon emissions indicators in both level and intensity are transformed into logarithms and standardized to facilitate interpretation.

Figure 3: Carbon premium (Emissions Level)

Note: The figure represents the estimated coefficient of β_1 from our baseline Equation 3 when considering emissions level. Note that each point in the figure represents the estimated coefficient corresponding to different specifications distinguished by the value of the considered climate law indicator on the x-axis.

(2021a). They found that brown companies exhibit higher realized returns than green ones because investors demand a compensation to carry this carbon transition risk. At this time, a crucial distinction between our study and theirs is the scope. First, their observation period ranging from 2005 to 2017 differs from ours. Then, their study encompasses a broader set of companies due to different sources for carbon emissions data: they use Trucost, while we draw from Thomson Reuters. As detailed in section subsection 2.3, our sample is constrained by the number of companies disclosing their carbon emissions data, leading to a smaller sample size. Furthermore, they argue that incorporating industry fixed effects can significantly alter results. We did not include industry fixed effects in our baseline estimation since we used a TWFE model, focusing specifically on US S&P 500 companies. In conclusion, our results are in line with recent studies, suggesting that green stocks may outperform their brown counterparts during times of heightened climate change concerns (Bauer et al., 2022; Aswani et al., 2023).

Figure 4: Carbon premium (Emissions Intensity)

Note: The figure represents the estimated coefficient of β_1 from our baseline Equation 3 when considering emissions intensity. Note that each point in the figure represents the estimated coefficient corresponding to different specifications distinguished by the value of the considered climate law indicator on the x-axis.

Figure 4 illustrates the fluctuations of the coefficient tied to emissions intensity across various specifications. We observe that although the coefficient hints at a positive sign, it doesn't show any statistical significance across all specifications in capturing a carbon premium based on emissions intensity. This trend is in line with the findings from Bolton and Kacperczyk (2021b,a, 2023). Bolton and Kacperczyk (2023) suggest that emissions intensity isn't a factor for investors when evaluating carbon risk premia. Such a perspective arises from the metric's inherent limitations. Even Garvey et al. (2018) emphasizes that an investor who takes a long position on low carbon intensity stocks outperforms another who opts for a short position on stocks with high emissions intensity, Bolton and Kacperczyk (2023) argue that large companies can appear disproportionately eco-friendly. A large company can decrease its emissions intensity while simultaneously increasing its overall emissions in the same year.

4.2 US Climate legislation and Pricing of the transition risk

Figure 5 illustrates the coefficient of the interaction term β_2 ¹⁷. The results provided displays the effect of reported total emissions after the enactment of climate laws on the stock returns of US S&P500 companies. We investigate the immediate and delayed effects of these laws for up to 12 months after the laws' enactment. Specifically, each point on the graph corresponds to the coefficient resulting from the interaction between carbon emissions and a dummy variable: this dummy takes on the value of 1 in the month the law is enacted (0M), 1 month afterwards (1M), and so on. We initially focus on total reported emissions as our indicator for carbon emissions.

Figure 5: Stock returns' response to US climate legislation (Emissions Level)

Note: The figure represents the estimated coefficient of β_2 from our baseline Equation 3 when considering emissions level. Note that each point in the figure represents the estimated coefficient corresponding to different specifications distinguished by the value of the considered climate law indicator on the x-axis.

First and foremost, we've observed a consistent negative sign for the interaction term between carbon emissions and our climate law indicator throughout various specifications. This aligns with our initial

¹⁷Confidence intervals have been computed at 90% level. The same chart, featuring both 95% and 99% confidence intervals, is provided in the Appendix D.

predictions. We anticipated that after the introduction of a climate law, “brown” or environmentally-unfriendly companies would face heightened penalties from the market due to climate regulations. This reasoning stems from the primary goal of many climate regulations, which is to reduce global greenhouse gas emissions. As such, companies with a larger carbon footprint, or “brown” companies, may be viewed as more vulnerable to these regulations and subsequently face steeper penalties.

To shed more light, when combining the coefficient related to carbon emissions with the interaction term’s coefficient, the negative impact of carbon emissions on stock returns becomes even more pronounced post-climate law enactment than when considering just the carbon emissions alone.

However, when viewed from an investment standpoint, this trend is less straightforward. A distinct change becomes evident from the second month after the enactment of the climate law. Initially, the interaction term’s coefficient shows statistical significance at the 1% level. For instance, given the interaction coefficient is estimated to be -0.336, after the implementation of the climate law (after the first month), a firm should expect a stock return of -3.139% against -2.803% without any climate law enactment or before its implementation. This estimation result suggests that 1 month subsequent to the introduction of new climate legislation, companies with high levels of carbon emissions tend to experience a consequent decline in their returns. But this level of significance decreases over the following months, fading by the sixth month post-enactment. This initial significance might be pointing to a short-lived “signal effect” following the climate law’s introduction. During this phase, investors may not be overly concerned about the real-world implications of the climate law, resulting in no additional discernible impact on the relationship between carbon emissions and stock returns.

However, a noticeable downturn is observed during the 6th and 7th months post-enactment, indicating a heightened negative impact. This suggests that during this medium-term phase, stock valuations may be influenced by carbon emission levels. This shift could be attributed to either the tangible effects of the climate law or merely investor perceptions in the half-year following the law’s introduction. Yet, this significant coefficient declines as we extend our observation, indicating that long-term investors might not factor in climate regulations when assessing carbon transition risks in the stock market.

In [Figure 6](#), we present results that shift our focus from carbon emissions level to emissions intensity. Emissions intensity is calculated by dividing carbon emissions by sales. This provides an adjusted view, essentially offering insights into how much carbon emission is produced for every unit of sales.

Turning our focus to the graph or table indicated by [Figure 6](#), it’s evident that the insights derived from it don’t significantly deviate from what we observed regarding the carbon emissions level. More specifically, the coefficient of the interaction term aligns with our anticipated results. It holds a negative value, reaffirming the notion that once climate laws come into play, carbon emissions adversely affect stock returns.

However, we discern that the coefficient’s value, regardless of which model specification we’re evaluating, is so proximate to 0 that it’s virtually indistinguishable from it. Such an observation is in line with our prior discussions. Given that we employ emissions intensity as the main indicator to measure a company’s susceptibility to the risks linked with transitioning away from carbon, these findings are expected. It signifies that during times when climate laws are enacted, investors appear to place greater emphasis on the total volume of a company’s carbon emissions rather than its emissions intensity. Given the overarching goal of climate regulations—restricting the global temperature increase to a threshold of 1.5° degrees—it’s understandable that investors prioritize the absolute carbon emissions of a company over its emissions intensity when assessing stock valuations.

Figure 6: Stock returns' response to US climate legislation (Emissions Intensity)

Note: The figure represents the estimated coefficient of β_2 from our baseline Equation 3 when considering emissions intensity. Note that each point in the figure represents the estimated coefficient corresponding to different specifications distinguished by the value of the considered climate law indicator on the x-axis.

4.3 General discussion

So, what does this translate to in terms of investor behavior? It suggests a nuanced perspective. In contrast with Bolton and Kacperczyk (2021a), we found an apparent premium linked to price adjustments without or before the climate law implementation. This is line with Pástor et al. (2022) supporting the idea that while brown firms might experience lower realized returns, they could simultaneously exhibit higher expected returns. Such a scenario might arise if the valuation of green assets has seen a spike in recent years due to a shift in investor preferences. Furthermore, investors appear to be weighing emissions level with more consideration when factoring in the risks that arise from climate change. In simpler terms, they're more focused on emissions level rather than just the raw emissions intensity, indicating a shift in how environmental risks are priced and perceived in the market.

Figure 5 gives insights on how carbon transition risk can be perceived given the U.S. climate legislation. This pattern suggests that given the uncertainty that often surrounds new legislation, many investors adopt a wait-and-see approach. They might wait to observe how companies adjust and what the actual financial ramifications are before making significant portfolio adjustments. Companies themselves might take a few months to communicate their strategic responses to the new laws. Investors might be waiting for clearer signals from company management about their mitigation strategies and potential impacts.

Furthermore, our data suggests that investors place a higher emphasis on carbon transition risk in the first month, as well as during the 6th and 7th months, following the enactment of climate laws. This implies that the financial market continues to penalize companies with notable carbon footprints, as defined by their emissions level. The coefficient of the interaction term is even more pronouncedly negative. A possible reason could be the market's adaptation to the new legislative context, with investors having gauged the law's ramifications and realigned their forecasts. Besides, following the implementation of climate legislation, companies that are seen to be compliant or proactive in their

approach might be viewed as environmental friendly. From an investor perspective, these companies may be perceived as forward-looking and better prepared for future regulatory shifts, leading to increased investor confidence. If legislation is seen as the first step toward a broader trend of increasing climate regulations, companies that adapt quickly are seen as better prepared for the future, making them more attractive investments.

Finally, the interaction term is significant exclusively for levels of carbon emissions in the baseline estimation. Particularly, regulations often target absolute emissions levels rather than intensity. Companies with high emissions may be more exposed to regulatory risks, carbon taxes, and other policy measures. This may offer insights into how investors view climate-related risks. One possible explanation is that investors might consider companies with high emission levels as being more vulnerable to climate-related legislation, and as a result, they might be more inclined to penalize such high-emitting firms. Besides, as discussed in Section 1, while emissions intensity can show efficiency or improvements in environmental performance, it does not provide a direct measure of a company's total impact on the environment [Bolton and Kacperczyk \(2021a\)](#). Investors concerned with the broader environmental impact might prioritize total emissions over intensity because a very large company could still have significant total emissions even if it has a low emissions intensity.

5 Further investigations

Our empirical results necessitate further exploration. Specifically, the estimation outcomes from [Figure 5](#) urge us to delve deeper into understanding the underlying factors that influence investor behavior. We're particularly interested in how they price carbon transition risks in the context of U.S. climate regulations during the timeframe of our empirical observations.

As discussed in the [Section 1](#), some empirical studies emphasize the link between climate awareness, regulatory changes, and their impacts on companies ([Busch et al., 2016](#); [Choi et al., 2020](#); [Guo et al., 2020](#); [Bolton and Kacperczyk, 2021a](#)). What are the reasons a priori to expect that the impact of climate law on the relationship between carbon emissions and stock returns increases with climate awareness?

Firstly, as climate awareness rises, investors might become more selective, often shunning companies not aligned with environmental goals due to potential regulatory risks and future liabilities. This can depress stock prices for high-emission firms. Additionally, growing environmental consciousness may sway investor preferences towards sustainable stocks. Concurrently, stricter climate regulations may impose fines or necessitate costly changes for high-emitting companies, impacting their financial performance. Thus, as these companies are perceived as riskier, investors seek higher returns for holding their stocks, leading to lower stock prices and subsequently, a stronger negative relationship between carbon emissions and stock returns ([Pástor et al., 2022](#); [Ardia et al., 2022](#)).

In this section, we focus on how heightened climate consciousness impacts the relationship between U.S. climate legislation, carbon emissions, and stock returns. To do this, we introduce a variable that we believe correlates with both carbon transition risk exposure and U.S. climate legislation. We postulate that a rise in climate awareness typically parallels tighter climate regulations. As a result, high carbon-emitting companies could encounter regulatory penalties, face operational challenges, or be compelled to undertake expensive modifications — factors that could dampen their financial health and, consequently, depress their stock returns. Consequently, we anticipate that as concerns about climate change increase, the negative effect of carbon emissions on stock returns becomes more pronounced.

Our measure for climate awareness stems from the coverage newspapers give to events related to climate change. The key idea is that media coverage can lead investors to reassess their views on climate risks and derive a renewed sense of ethical fulfillment from investing in eco-friendly companies. To represent the newspaper coverage surrounding climate change, we employ a time-series indicator taken from [Engle et al. \(2020\)](#). This indicator is derived from a textual examination of news sources, utilizing the proprietary sentiment measure from Crimson Hexagon. It specifically hones in on negative coverage concerning climate change, sourced from an extensive collection of over one trillion news articles¹⁸. Their indicator ends in May 2018. After merging it with our main database, the observation timeframe for this section extends from January 2010 to May 2018, resulting in 14,105 observations.

The graph in [Figure 7](#) showcases the climate change concerns time-series indicator from [Engle et al. \(2020\)](#), recorded monthly over our sample observation period. A higher value in this indicator suggests heightened awareness and concerns about the impact of climate change.

The trajectory of the indicator reveals a general upward trend over time, with peaks indicating periods of heightened climate change apprehension. Notably, the indicator peaks around early 2016, coinciding with the Paris Agreement. Given that the indicator incorporates sentiment analysis, it might not only capture concerns related to extreme weather events or the prevalence of climate-related

¹⁸Results obtained using the climate awareness metric from [Ardia et al. \(2022\)](#) are available upon request.

Figure 7: Climate Awareness Time-Series Indicator

Source: [Engle et al. \(2020\)](#).

discussions but also their intensity or sentiment. A surge in the indicator might indicate the media’s usage of more dire or urgent language regarding climate change.

Our approach to estimation involves breaking down our primary variable of interest, “Emissions \times Law”, based on the levels of climate concerns. We segment this variable into four distinct variables, each corresponding to a specific degree of climate concern. For the forthcoming results, we focus on “Emissions \times Law” during periods of high climate concerns, specifically selecting observations that exceed the threshold of the fourth quartile¹⁹.

Figure 8 illustrates the coefficient of the interaction term (identical to the baseline estimation) for periods of heightened climate change concerns. These findings align well with our initial hypotheses. Interestingly, while the coefficient isn’t statistically significant at the 0M mark (the month when the law came into effect) and a month later, its significance grows from the second month post climate law enactment, continuing up to the 11th month. This implies that in periods of heightened climate awareness, the negative effect of carbon emissions on stock returns begins to manifest two months post the implementation of a climate law and remains notable for nearly a year. During periods of heightened climate change awareness, investors appear to place greater weight on the risks associated with climate change, leading to more significant penalization of companies with high carbon emissions. This heightened awareness seems to magnify the perceived stringency of climate regulations, making investors more vigilant in how they price in carbon transition risks into their stock valuations. Essentially, intensified climate concerns amplify the effects of U.S. climate legislation on the relationship between carbon emissions and stock returns, underlying a trend where investors are integrating climate risks more strongly into their assets evaluations. Especially, high-emission companies are viewed as increasingly riskier, particularly when climate awareness are pronounced and in the wake of new climate-related legal frameworks.

Besides, the discernable lag – the pronounced negative relationship between carbon emissions and stock returns emerging two months after the introduction of climate laws – indicates that investors don’t react immediately. Instead, they seem to adopt a more measured approach, taking the time to

¹⁹Results for periods with medium and low levels of climate change concerns can be found in the Appendix.

Figure 8: Stock returns' response to US climate legislation - High Climate Change Concerns (Emissions Level)

Note: The figure represents the estimated coefficient of β_2 from our baseline Equation 3 when considering both emissions level and high climate change concerns periods. Note that each point in the figure represents the estimated coefficient corresponding to different specifications distinguished by the value of the considered climate law indicator on the x-axis.

understand, interpret, and respond to the nuances of the new regulations. This suggests a contemplative assessment of the legislation's medium to long-term ramifications for businesses.

However, the significant negative impact of carbon emissions on stock returns disappears 12 months after the introduction of a climate law. This indicates that, over the long run, even the period of high climate awareness, the U.S. climate legislation doesn't further influence the relationship between carbon emissions and stock returns. This could be interpreted as investors, over time, perceiving the climate laws as either insufficiently stringent or not effectively implemented to perpetually influence their stock valuation decisions in light of the existing climate regulations. In essence, while climate awareness and legislation can have a pronounced impact on stock returns, especially for high carbon-emitting firms, these effects might not be persistent in the long run without continuous reinforcement.

6 Conclusion

In this paper, we empirically investigate how the U.S. climate legislation influence the relationship between carbon emissions and stock returns over the 2010-2019 period. Specifically, our research objectives are twofold.

Firstly, our study aims to answer the question of whether carbon emissions are reflected in stock prices. Our primary indicator for measuring the carbon transition risk is the reported total carbon emissions. Among the ongoing debate surrounding the pricing of transition risk on stock market, our findings indicate a discernible investor attention to carbon risks. Our estimates reveals a noteworthy pattern: companies with lower carbon emissions generate higher realized returns. However, when focusing on emissions intensity, discern any apparent premium linked to market shifts when using emissions intensity as a main indicator for a company's greenness (Bolton and Kacperczyk, 2021a).

Secondly, our analysis extends to understanding how U.S. climate legislation influences the dynamics between carbon emissions and stock returns. Using a publicly available database on national climate laws, we construct a climate law index. Our analysis suggests a 2.8% decrease in stock returns following the enactment of a climate law, on average. Our findings indicate a intricate relationship between investors' valuation of carbon transition risk and the enactment of climate laws. Notably, we observed a marked effect of carbon emissions on stock returns within a month following the introduction of the climate law and continuing into the medium term. This raises concerns about the regulation's ability to ensure sustained long-term outcomes. Besides, it seems that investors account for carbon transition primarily based on carbon emission levels and to a larger degree once climate laws come into play. This reinforces the notion that investors continue to penalize high-emission companies in the face of climate legislation. Given that climate policies frequently aim at company emission levels to meet global greenhouse gas reduction targets, the context of these regulations might be influenced by how companies communicate their efforts to reduce emissions or internalize associated costs. However, when assessing the pricing of carbon transition risks on U.S. S&P 500 companies, our results suggest that climate regulations might not be considered by long-term investors.

Then, using a climate awareness indicator derived from major U.S. newspapers, further investigations reveal that during times of high concerns about climate change, the negative effect of carbon emissions on stock returns is amplified following U.S. climate legislation.

Our paper calls for several extensions. On one hand, it would be relevant to assess the relationship between carbon emissions and stock returns, primarily considering the location of the company's headquarters. Indeed, certain states may be subject to specific regulations while others are not. On the other hand, it could also be of interest to examine whether the state in which the company operates is Republican or Democrat. The political segmentation in the United States leads to different directions in terms of combating climate change, leading to empirical results that could completely diverge.

In conclusion, our empirical findings bear significant implications for environmental policy-making. Specifically, our research sheds light on the market's approach to pricing climate risk and how climate regulations play a role in influencing this pricing mechanism. The long-term implications of U.S. legislation on the relationship between carbon emissions and stock returns warrant reinforcement. Current legislative measures appear to have a more pronounced influence in the medium term, However the sustainability and longevity of these impacts remain uncertain. Ensuring that financial markets consistently and progressively reward eco-friendly corporate behavior is key to driving long-lasting environmental change. To achieve this, policymakers should consider refining and bolstering the existing regulations, ensuring they not only respond to immediate concerns but also lay a solid foundation for

long-term market adjustments in favor of a lower-carbon economy.

References

- Akaike, H. (1974). A new look at the statistical model identification. *IEEE transactions on automatic control*, 19(6):716–723.
- Alessi, L., Ossola, E., and Panzica, R. (2021). What greenium matters in the stock market? the role of greenhouse gas emissions and environmental disclosures. *Journal of Financial Stability*, 54:100869.
- Ardia, D., Bluteau, K., Boudt, K., and Inghelbrecht, K. (2022). Climate change concerns and the performance of green vs. brown stocks. *Management Science*.
- Aswani, J., Raghunandan, A., and Rajgopal, S. (2023). Are carbon emissions associated with stock returns? *Review of Finance*, forthcoming.
- Bauer, M. D., Huber, D., Rudebusch, G. D., and Wilms, O. (2022). Where is the carbon premium? global performance of green and brown stocks. *Journal of Climate Finance*, 1:100006.
- Bernardini, E., Di Giampaolo, J., Faiella, I., and Poli, R. (2021). The impact of carbon risk on stock returns: evidence from the european electric utilities. *Journal of Sustainable Finance & Investment*, 11(1):1–26.
- Bolton, P. and Kacperczyk, M. (2021a). Do investors care about carbon risk? *Journal of financial economics*, 142(2):517–549.
- Bolton, P. and Kacperczyk, M. (2021b). Global pricing of carbon-transition risk. Technical report, National Bureau of Economic Research.
- Bolton, P. and Kacperczyk, M. (2023). Are carbon emissions associated with stock returns? comment. *Review of Finance*, page rfad019.
- Borghesi, S., Castellini, M., Comincioli, N., Donadelli, M., Guffer, I., and Vergalli, S. (2022). European green policy announcements and sectoral stock returns. *Energy Policy*, 166:113004.
- Busch, T., Bauer, R., and Orlitzky, M. (2016). Sustainable development and financial markets: Old paths and new avenues. *Business & Society*, 55(3):303–329.
- Busch, T., Johnson, M., and Pioch, T. (2022). Corporate carbon performance data: Quo vadis? *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, 26(1):350–363.
- Campiglio, E., Monnin, P., and von Jagow, A. (2019). Climate risk in financial assets. Concil on Economic Policy Discussion Note 2019 2.
- Choi, D., Gao, Z., and Jiang, W. (2020). Attention to global warming. *The Review of Financial Studies*, 33(3):1112–1145.
- El Ouadghiri, I., Guesmi, K., Peillex, J., and Ziegler, A. (2021). Public attention to environmental issues and stock market returns. *Ecological economics*, 180:106836.
- Engle, R. F., Giglio, S., Kelly, B., Lee, H., and Stroebel, J. (2020). Hedging climate change news. *The Review of Financial Studies*, 33(3):1184–1216.
- Eskander, S. M. and Fankhauser, S. (2020). Reduction in greenhouse gas emissions from national climate legislation. *Nature Climate Change*, 10(8):750–756.

- Faccini, R., Matin, R., and Skiadopoulos, G. (2023). Dissecting climate risks: Are they reflected in stock prices? *Journal of Banking & Finance*, page 106948.
- Garvey, G. T., Iyer, M., and Nash, J. (2018). Carbon footprint and productivity: does the “e” in esg capture efficiency as well as environment. *Journal of Investment Management*, 16(1):59–69.
- Giglio, S., Kelly, B., and Stroebe, J. (2021). Climate finance. *Annual Review of Financial Economics*, 13:15–36.
- Görgen, M., Jacob, A., Nerlinger, M., Riordan, R., Rohleder, M., and Wilkens, M. (2020). Carbon risk. *Available at SSRN 2930897*.
- Guo, M., Kuai, Y., and Liu, X. (2020). Stock market response to environmental policies: Evidence from heavily polluting firms in china. *Economic Modelling*, 86:306–316.
- Hengge, M., Panizza, U., and Varghese, M. R. (2023). *Carbon policy surprises and stock returns: Signals from financial markets*. International Monetary Fund. Paper no. 17868.
- Hsu, P.-h., Li, K., and Tsou, C.-y. (2023). The pollution premium. *The Journal of Finance*, 78(3):1343–1392.
- Ilhan, E., Sautner, Z., and Vilkov, G. (2021). Carbon tail risk. *The Review of Financial Studies*, 34(3):1540–1571.
- Krueger, P., Sautner, Z., and Starks, L. T. (2020). The importance of climate risks for institutional investors. *The Review of Financial Studies*, 33(3):1067–1111.
- Monasterolo, I. and De Angelis, L. (2020). Blind to carbon risk? an analysis of stock market reaction to the paris agreement. *Ecological Economics*, 170:106571.
- Oestreich, A. M. and Tsiakas, I. (2015). Carbon emissions and stock returns: Evidence from the EU emissions trading scheme. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 58:294–308.
- Pástor, L., Stambaugh, R. F., and Taylor, L. A. (2022). Dissecting green returns. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 146(2):403–424.
- Sautner, Z., Van Lent, L., Vilkov, G., and Zhang, R. (2023). Firm-level climate change exposure. *The Journal of Finance*, 78(3):1449–1498.
- Schwarz, G. (1978). Estimating the dimension of a model. *The annals of statistics*, pages 461–464.
- Witkowski, P., Adamczyk, A., and Franek, S. (2021). Does carbon risk matter? evidence of carbon premium in eu energy-intensive companies. *Energies*, 14(7):1855.

A Descriptive statistics

Table A-1: Descriptive statistics of the dependent variable

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min.	Max.	N
Returns	0.866	7.506	-28.252	24.951	27191

Source: Author's computation.

Table A-2: Summary statistics

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min.	Max.	N
Size	17.14	1.157	14.128	20.989	17180
Tobin Q	1.324	0.784	-0.446	4.089	17180
Debt	0.279	0.142	0	0.708	17180
Book-to-market	0.344	0.241	-0.123	1.538	17180
PPE	0.222	0.187	0.018	0.932	17180
R&D	0.043	0.051	0	0.399	17180
Sales growth	0.063	0.155	-0.402	1.109	17180
Momentum	11.157	23.168	-84.016	81.626	17180
Investment-to-assets	-3.571	0.729	-7.436	-1.531	17180
ROE	25.575	33.81	-68.430	237.94	17180

Source: Author's computation.

B Corresponding tables to estimation results from baseline **Equation 3**

Table B-1 refers to **Figure 3** and **Figure 5** in Section 4. Table B-2 corresponds to **Figure 4** and **Figure 6** in the same section.

Table B-1: Responses of stock returns to Climate laws (Emissions Level)

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)	(13)
Emissions	-2.817*** (0.825)	-2.803*** (0.827)	-2.810*** (0.827)	-2.814*** (0.828)	-2.802*** (0.827)	-2.802*** (0.828)	-2.769*** (0.829)	-2.761*** (0.830)	-2.778*** (0.831)	-2.780*** (0.831)	-2.806*** (0.829)	-2.810*** (0.828)	-2.812*** (0.828)
Law Event × Emissions	-0.196 (0.208)												
1M Dummy × Emissions		-0.336** (0.160)											
2M Dummy × Emissions			-0.154 (0.138)										
3M Dummy × Emissions				-0.074 (0.152)									
4M Dummy × Emissions					-0.148 (0.131)								
5M Dummy × Emissions						-0.121 (0.139)							
6M Dummy × Emissions							-0.273* (0.140)						
7M Dummy × Emissions								-0.285** (0.130)					
8M Dummy × Emissions									-0.192 (0.132)				
9M Dummy × Emissions										-0.170 (0.125)			
10M Dummy × Emissions											-0.063 (0.121)		
11M Dummy × Emissions												-0.046 (0.131)	
12M Dummy × Emissions													-0.033 (0.135)
Size	3.731*** (0.275)	3.714*** (0.274)	3.721*** (0.275)	3.726*** (0.276)	3.712*** (0.275)	3.713*** (0.276)	3.676*** (0.275)	3.669*** (0.276)	3.688*** (0.278)	3.691*** (0.278)	3.719*** (0.279)	3.723*** (0.278)	3.726*** (0.278)
Tobin Q	-1.775*** (0.364)	-1.779*** (0.364)	-1.778*** (0.364)	-1.777*** (0.364)	-1.780*** (0.365)	-1.780*** (0.364)	-1.791*** (0.365)	-1.795*** (0.366)	-1.791*** (0.365)	-1.791*** (0.365)	-1.782*** (0.364)	-1.780*** (0.363)	-1.779*** (0.364)
Debt	3.974*** (1.259)	3.947*** (1.255)	3.962*** (1.258)	3.972*** (1.261)	3.948*** (1.258)	3.951*** (1.260)	3.894*** (1.255)	3.886*** (1.255)	3.917*** (1.259)	3.921*** (1.258)	3.962*** (1.263)	3.963*** (1.264)	3.972*** (1.264)
Book-to-market	2.176* (1.129)	2.172* (1.128)	2.170* (1.128)	2.174* (1.128)	2.168* (1.129)	2.166* (1.129)	2.144* (1.131)	2.130* (1.133)	2.141* (1.133)	2.140* (1.133)	2.160* (1.130)	2.164* (1.129)	2.166* (1.129)
PPE	3.864 (2.701)	3.887 (2.697)	3.878 (2.700)	3.869 (2.703)	3.887 (2.696)	3.884 (2.699)	3.949 (2.692)	3.949 (2.693)	3.929 (2.703)	3.929 (2.699)	3.885 (2.705)	3.878 (2.701)	3.870 (2.701)
R&D	27.127*** (7.844)	26.978*** (7.859)	27.082*** (7.858)	27.140*** (7.851)	27.055*** (7.873)	27.069*** (7.861)	26.884*** (7.900)	26.884*** (7.900)	26.980*** (7.898)	27.020*** (7.901)	27.151*** (7.856)	27.171*** (7.853)	27.183*** (7.848)
Sales growth	-0.300 (0.538)	-0.289 (0.537)	-0.293 (0.537)	-0.296 (0.537)	-0.290 (0.535)	-0.293 (0.536)	-0.284 (0.533)	-0.284 (0.533)	-0.298 (0.534)	-0.302 (0.535)	-0.305 (0.537)	-0.305 (0.537)	-0.304 (0.537)
Momentum	-0.014*** (0.003)												
Investment	-0.353 (0.267)	-0.350 (0.266)	-0.352 (0.267)	-0.353 (0.267)	-0.352 (0.267)	-0.352 (0.267)	-0.351 (0.267)	-0.351 (0.267)	-0.353 (0.268)	-0.352 (0.269)	-0.355 (0.268)	-0.355 (0.268)	-0.355 (0.268)
ROE	0.012*** (0.004)												
Firms FE	Yes												
Time FE	Yes												
Firms Cluster	Yes												
R ²	0.364	0.364	0.364	0.364	0.364	0.364	0.364	0.364	0.364	0.364	0.364	0.364	0.364
Observations	17079	17079	17079	17079	17079	17079	17079	17079	17079	17079	17079	17079	17079

Significance levels are: * p < 0.10; ** p < 0.05; *** p < 0.01

Table B-2: Responses of stock returns to Climate laws (Emissions Intensity)

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)	(13)
Emissions	0.738 (0.747)	0.766 (0.750)	0.759 (0.751)	0.748 (0.753)	0.764 (0.751)	0.776 (0.755)	0.817 (0.756)	0.818 (0.757)	0.801 (0.760)	0.800 (0.757)	0.783 (0.758)	0.783 (0.757)	0.781 (0.761)
Law Event × Emissions	-0.219 (0.291)												
1M Dummy × Emissions		-0.446* (0.244)											
2M Dummy × Emissions			-0.247 (0.199)										
3M Dummy × Emissions				-0.125 (0.219)									
4M Dummy × Emissions					-0.180 (0.183)								
5M Dummy × Emissions						-0.202 (0.197)							
6M Dummy × Emissions							-0.330 (0.204)						
7M Dummy × Emissions								-0.307 (0.187)					
8M Dummy × Emissions									-0.228 (0.187)				
9M Dummy × Emissions										-0.210 (0.190)			
10M Dummy × Emissions											-0.148 (0.175)		
11M Dummy × Emissions												-0.136 (0.184)	
12M Dummy × Emissions													-0.114 (0.194)
Size	3.366*** (0.285)	3.353*** (0.284)	3.356*** (0.285)	3.361*** (0.284)	3.354*** (0.284)	3.348*** (0.283)	3.331*** (0.282)	3.331*** (0.282)	3.330*** (0.283)	3.340*** (0.284)	3.348*** (0.284)	3.348*** (0.284)	3.351*** (0.284)
Tobin Q	-1.576*** (0.375)	-1.584*** (0.375)	-1.583*** (0.375)	-1.580*** (0.375)	-1.584*** (0.376)	-1.588*** (0.376)	-1.598*** (0.376)	-1.600*** (0.376)	-1.595*** (0.376)	-1.595*** (0.376)	-1.590*** (0.376)	-1.590*** (0.376)	-1.589*** (0.375)
Debt	3.061** (1.313)	3.032** (1.307)	3.038** (1.310)	3.049** (1.313)	3.032** (1.309)	3.022** (1.308)	2.985** (1.302)	2.987** (1.303)	3.006** (1.307)	3.006** (1.307)	3.022** (1.310)	3.022** (1.313)	3.026** (1.314)
Book-to-market	2.000* (1.179)	1.985* (1.178)	1.983* (1.178)	1.991* (1.178)	1.980* (1.180)	1.970* (1.179)	1.936 (1.182)	1.929 (1.183)	1.943 (1.185)	1.941 (1.188)	1.953 (1.184)	1.953 (1.183)	1.959* (1.184)
PPE	1.461 (3.037)	1.451 (3.032)	1.452 (3.030)	1.454 (3.029)	1.447 (3.028)	1.441 (3.025)	1.426 (3.023)	1.433 (3.026)	1.443 (3.029)	1.446 (3.033)	1.449 (3.033)	1.446 (3.034)	1.442 (3.033)
R&D	27.233*** (6.889)	27.118*** (6.876)	27.167*** (6.889)	27.212*** (6.890)	27.174*** (6.889)	27.148*** (6.886)	27.066*** (6.877)	27.079*** (6.882)	27.129*** (6.891)	27.154*** (6.895)	27.207*** (6.891)	27.220*** (6.893)	27.234*** (6.895)
Sales growth	-0.097 (0.604)	-0.093 (0.603)	-0.092 (0.603)	-0.094 (0.603)	-0.093 (0.603)	-0.094 (0.603)	-0.096 (0.602)	-0.099 (0.602)	-0.101 (0.603)	-0.103 (0.604)	-0.103 (0.605)	-0.102 (0.605)	-0.101 (0.605)
Momentum	-0.013*** (0.003)												
Investment	-0.363 (0.268)	-0.365 (0.268)	-0.364 (0.269)	-0.363 (0.269)	-0.365 (0.269)	-0.367 (0.269)	-0.373 (0.270)	-0.373 (0.271)	-0.371 (0.272)	-0.371 (0.271)	-0.369 (0.271)	-0.369 (0.271)	-0.368 (0.271)
ROE	0.011*** (0.004)												
Firms FE	Yes												
Time FE	Yes												
Firms Cluster	Yes												
R ²	0.362	0.362	0.362	0.362	0.362	0.362	0.362	0.362	0.362	0.362	0.362	0.362	0.362
Observations	17079	17079	17079	17079	17079	17079	17079	17079	17079	17079	17079	17079	17079

Significance levels are: * p < 0.10; ** p < 0.05; *** p < 0.01

C Additional tables and figures

In [Figure C-1](#), [Figure C-2](#), [Figure C-3](#) and [Figure C-4](#), we present the estimation results without lagging the carbon emissions indicator by one period for both intensity and level measures. This approach aligns with the methodology initiated by [Bolton and Kacperczyk \(2021b\)](#), wherein monthly stock returns are regressed on carbon emissions from the same year.

Therefore, we estimate the following model:

$$r_{i,t} = \beta_0 + \theta_i + \gamma_t + \beta_1 CO2_{i,t} + \beta_2 CO2_{i,t} \times LAW_t + \sum_{k=3}^K \beta_k X_{k,i,t-1} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (\text{C-1})$$

[Table C-1](#) and [Table C-2](#) refer to the corresponding estimation tables.

[Table C-3](#) and [Table C-4](#) refer to estimation results provided in [Section 5](#).

Figure C-1: Carbon premium with no emissions lag (Emissions Level)

Note: The figure represents the estimated coefficient of β_1 from Equation C-1 when considering emissions level. Note that each point in the figure represents the estimated coefficient corresponding to different specifications distinguished by the value of the considered climate law indicator on the x-axis.

Figure C-2: Carbon premium with no emissions lag (Emissions Intensity)

Note: The figure represents the estimated coefficient of β_1 from Equation C-1 when considering emissions intensity. Note that each point in the figure represents the estimated coefficient corresponding to different specifications distinguished by the value of the considered climate law indicator on the x-axis.

Figure C-3: Stock returns' response to US climate legislation with no emissions lag (Emissions Level)

Note: The figure represents the estimated coefficient of β_2 from Equation C-1 when considering emissions level. Note that each point in the figure represents the estimated coefficient corresponding to different specifications distinguished by the value of the considered climate law indicator on the x-axis.

Figure C-4: Stock returns' response to US climate legislation with no emissions lag (Emissions Intensity)

Note: The figure represents the estimated coefficient of β_2 from Equation C-1 when considering emissions intensity. Note that each point in the figure represents the estimated coefficient corresponding to different specifications distinguished by the value of the considered climate law indicator on the x-axis.

Table C-1: Responses of stock returns to Climate laws with no emissions publication lag (Emissions Level)

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)	(13)
Emissions	-3.289*** (0.845)	-3.266*** (0.848)	-3.270*** (0.848)	-3.277*** (0.849)	-3.272*** (0.849)	-3.271*** (0.849)	-3.229*** (0.851)	-3.219*** (0.851)	-3.241*** (0.851)	-3.243*** (0.851)	-3.287*** (0.848)	-3.289*** (0.845)	-3.298*** (0.847)
Law Event × Emissions	-0.105 (0.230)												
1M Dummy × Emissions		-0.323** (0.154)											
2M Dummy × Emissions			-0.182 (0.131)										
3M Dummy × Emissions				-0.096 (0.138)									
4M Dummy × Emissions					-0.101 (0.119)								
5M Dummy × Emissions						-0.094 (0.127)							
6M Dummy × Emissions							-0.244* (0.131)						
7M Dummy × Emissions								-0.261** (0.121)					
8M Dummy × Emissions									-0.170 (0.120)				
9M Dummy × Emissions										-0.154 (0.119)			
10M Dummy × Emissions											-0.018 (0.114)		
11M Dummy × Emissions												-0.011 (0.130)	
12M Dummy × Emissions													0.011 (0.133)
Size	3.854*** (0.287)	3.837*** (0.287)	3.839*** (0.287)	3.844*** (0.289)	3.841*** (0.288)	3.839*** (0.288)	3.806*** (0.287)	3.798*** (0.286)	3.816*** (0.287)	3.818*** (0.288)	3.852*** (0.289)	3.854*** (0.287)	3.860*** (0.288)
TobinQ	-1.996*** (0.361)	-2.001*** (0.362)	-2.000*** (0.361)	-1.999*** (0.361)	-2.000*** (0.362)	-2.000*** (0.362)	-2.011*** (0.363)	-2.016*** (0.363)	-2.010*** (0.363)	-2.011*** (0.362)	-1.997*** (0.361)	-1.997*** (0.361)	-1.994*** (0.361)
Debt	4.432*** (1.196)	4.414*** (1.194)	4.416*** (1.194)	4.421*** (1.194)	4.417*** (1.194)	4.414*** (1.195)	4.373*** (1.191)	4.363*** (1.190)	4.385*** (1.193)	4.385*** (1.193)	4.429*** (1.199)	4.431*** (1.201)	4.440*** (1.201)
Book-to-market	2.102** (1.042)	2.095** (1.041)	2.094** (1.041)	2.098** (1.042)	2.096** (1.042)	2.094** (1.042)	2.070** (1.044)	2.058* (1.045)	2.071** (1.046)	2.069** (1.044)	2.099** (1.044)	2.100** (1.043)	2.106** (1.043)
PPE	5.152*** (2.352)	5.194*** (2.344)	5.182*** (2.346)	5.168*** (2.349)	5.174*** (2.346)	5.176*** (2.348)	5.241*** (2.332)	5.268*** (2.330)	5.236*** (2.343)	5.238*** (2.338)	5.156*** (2.354)	5.151*** (2.353)	5.137*** (2.353)
R&D	27.866*** (8.469)	27.666*** (8.475)	27.738*** (8.482)	27.804*** (8.478)	27.795*** (8.485)	27.792*** (8.473)	27.601*** (8.499)	27.567*** (8.518)	27.677*** (8.503)	27.702*** (8.513)	27.884*** (8.467)	27.893*** (8.461)	27.916*** (8.459)
Sales growth	-0.481 (0.483)	-0.468 (0.482)	-0.468 (0.482)	-0.472 (0.483)	-0.472 (0.482)	-0.473 (0.482)	-0.463 (0.480)	-0.466 (0.479)	-0.475 (0.480)	-0.479 (0.482)	-0.483 (0.482)	-0.483 (0.482)	-0.483 (0.482)
Momentum	-0.015*** (0.003)												
Investment	-0.313 (0.258)	-0.309 (0.257)	-0.310 (0.257)	-0.311 (0.258)	-0.311 (0.258)	-0.311 (0.258)	-0.309 (0.258)	-0.310 (0.258)	-0.312 (0.259)	-0.312 (0.259)	-0.314 (0.258)	-0.314 (0.258)	-0.314 (0.258)
ROE	0.014*** (0.003)												
Firms FE	Yes												
Time FE	Yes												
Firms Cluster	Yes												
R ²	0.368	0.368	0.368	0.368	0.368	0.368	0.368	0.368	0.368	0.368	0.368	0.368	0.368
Observations	17727	17727	17727	17727	17727	17727	17727	17727	17727	17727	17727	17727	17727

Significance levels are: * p < 0.10; ** p < 0.05; *** p < 0.01

Table C-2: Responses of stock returns to Climate laws with no emissions publication lag (Emissions Intensity)

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)	(13)
Emissions	0.213 (0.774)	0.257 (0.780)	0.257 (0.782)	0.247 (0.785)	0.254 (0.784)	0.269 (0.790)	0.319 (0.793)	0.319 (0.792)	0.293 (0.796)	0.284 (0.794)	0.245 (0.793)	0.247 (0.790)	0.232 (0.796)
Law Event × Emissions	-0.117 (0.308)												
1M Dummy × Emissions		-0.465* (0.238)											
2M Dummy × Emissions			-0.305 (0.196)										
3M Dummy × Emissions				-0.185 (0.208)									
4M Dummy × Emissions					-0.180 (0.172)								
5M Dummy × Emissions						-0.200 (0.187)							
6M Dummy × Emissions							-0.325* (0.194)						
7M Dummy × Emissions								-0.298* (0.176)					
8M Dummy × Emissions									-0.210 (0.176)				
9M Dummy × Emissions										-0.173 (0.182)			
10M Dummy × Emissions											-0.081 (0.166)		
11M Dummy × Emissions												-0.078 (0.179)	
12M Dummy × Emissions													-0.046 (0.188)
Size	3.334*** (0.278)	3.321*** (0.277)	3.321*** (0.277)	3.323*** (0.277)	3.322*** (0.277)	3.317*** (0.276)	3.302*** (0.275)	3.302*** (0.275)	3.310*** (0.275)	3.313*** (0.276)	3.325*** (0.276)	3.325*** (0.277)	3.329*** (0.278)
Tobin Q	-1.764*** (0.374)	-1.774*** (0.374)	-1.775*** (0.374)	-1.772*** (0.375)	-1.773*** (0.375)	-1.776*** (0.375)	-1.787*** (0.376)	-1.787*** (0.376)	-1.781*** (0.376)	-1.779*** (0.375)	-1.771*** (0.374)	-1.771*** (0.374)	-1.768*** (0.374)
Debt	3.604*** (1.264)	3.581*** (1.258)	3.578*** (1.258)	3.582*** (1.259)	3.577*** (1.258)	3.567*** (1.257)	3.534*** (1.251)	3.534*** (1.252)	3.552*** (1.255)	3.556*** (1.257)	3.581*** (1.263)	3.580*** (1.266)	3.590*** (1.268)
Book-to-market	1.875* (1.093)	1.852* (1.092)	1.848* (1.093)	1.856* (1.093)	1.852* (1.094)	1.842* (1.094)	1.807 (1.098)	1.803 (1.100)	1.821* (1.101)	1.826* (1.102)	1.851* (1.097)	1.851* (1.096)	1.862* (1.097)
PPE	2.389 (2.732)	2.386 (2.725)	2.381 (2.723)	2.378 (2.723)	2.377 (2.722)	2.372 (2.719)	2.362 (2.713)	2.373 (2.715)	2.381 (2.720)	2.385 (2.728)	2.387 (2.728)	2.384 (2.728)	2.384 (2.730)
R&D	27.890*** (7.252)	27.712*** (7.228)	27.749*** (7.241)	27.799*** (7.243)	27.799*** (7.245)	27.771*** (7.238)	27.673*** (7.224)	27.678*** (7.231)	27.734*** (7.242)	27.769*** (7.251)	27.853*** (7.253)	27.861*** (7.255)	27.887*** (7.261)
Sales growth	-0.322 (0.498)	-0.318 (0.499)	-0.315 (0.498)	-0.316 (0.497)	-0.316 (0.497)	-0.316 (0.498)	-0.316 (0.498)	-0.316 (0.498)	-0.321 (0.498)	-0.322 (0.499)	-0.323 (0.498)	-0.323 (0.498)	-0.322 (0.498)
Momentum	-0.014*** (0.003)												
Investment	-0.321 (0.267)	-0.322 (0.266)	-0.322 (0.266)	-0.321 (0.267)	-0.323 (0.267)	-0.324 (0.267)	-0.329 (0.268)	-0.330 (0.269)	-0.328 (0.269)	-0.324 (0.269)	-0.324 (0.269)	-0.324 (0.269)	-0.323 (0.268)
ROE	0.013*** (0.004)												
Firms FE	Yes												
Time FE	Yes												
Firms Cluster	Yes												
R ²	0.365	0.366	0.365	0.365	0.365	0.365	0.366	0.366	0.365	0.365	0.365	0.365	0.365
Observations	17727	17727	17727	17727	17727	17727	17727	17727	17727	17727	17727	17727	17727

Significance levels are: * p < 0.10; ** p < 0.05; *** p < 0.01

Table C-3: Responses of stock returns to Climate laws - High period of Climate Awareness (Emissions Level)

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)	(13)
Emissions	-2.196** (0.865)	-2.188** (0.866)	-2.218** (0.867)	-2.251*** (0.865)	-2.233** (0.865)	-2.233** (0.864)	-2.217** (0.866)	-2.211** (0.867)	-2.233** (0.867)	-2.233** (0.867)	-2.244** (0.867)	-2.228** (0.866)	-2.217** (0.865)
High Concerns - Law Event × Emissions													
High Concerns - 1M Dummy × Emissions		0.100 (0.348)											
High Concerns - 2M Dummy × Emissions			-0.651* (0.333)										
High Concerns - 3M Dummy × Emissions				-1.036*** (0.394)									
High Concerns - 4M Dummy × Emissions					-0.779** (0.390)								
High Concerns - 5M Dummy × Emissions						-0.650* (0.342)							
High Concerns - 6M Dummy × Emissions							-0.648** (0.313)						
High Concerns - 7M Dummy × Emissions								-0.537* (0.279)					
High Concerns - 8M Dummy × Emissions									-0.712** (0.296)				
High Concerns - 9M Dummy × Emissions										-0.684** (0.287)			
High Concerns - 10M Dummy × Emissions											-0.735*** (0.276)		
High Concerns - 11M Dummy × Emissions												-0.620** (0.277)	
High Concerns - 12M Dummy × Emissions													-0.432 (0.289)
Size	4.099*** (0.352)	4.087*** (0.351)	4.114*** (0.354)	4.157*** (0.355)	4.122*** (0.352)	4.131*** (0.354)	4.085*** (0.351)	4.078*** (0.352)	4.106*** (0.354)	4.104*** (0.354)	4.114*** (0.356)	4.096*** (0.356)	4.106*** (0.356)
TobinQ	-1.732*** (0.409)	-1.732*** (0.409)	-1.732*** (0.409)	-1.730*** (0.411)	-1.738*** (0.411)	-1.731*** (0.409)	-1.742*** (0.411)	-1.744*** (0.411)	-1.736*** (0.409)	-1.735*** (0.409)	-1.730*** (0.409)	-1.737*** (0.408)	-1.733*** (0.409)
Debt	4.021*** (1.385)	4.006*** (1.383)	4.025*** (1.391)	4.076*** (1.402)	4.021*** (1.393)	4.052*** (1.398)	3.966*** (1.385)	3.965*** (1.386)	4.001*** (1.394)	3.998*** (1.392)	4.013*** (1.395)	3.992*** (1.393)	4.018*** (1.395)
Book-to-market	3.103** (1.407)	3.102** (1.406)	3.101** (1.408)	3.099** (1.409)	3.091** (1.410)	3.107** (1.407)	3.077** (1.409)	3.069** (1.410)	3.092** (1.409)	3.096** (1.411)	3.115** (1.408)	3.095** (1.407)	3.105** (1.408)
PPE	3.689 (2.963)	3.703 (2.967)	3.691 (2.970)	3.650 (2.970)	3.710 (2.968)	3.661 (2.960)	3.766 (2.977)	3.770 (2.973)	3.699 (2.960)	3.658 (2.950)	3.658 (2.940)	3.707 (2.938)	3.660 (2.934)
R&D	22.914** (8.983)	22.866** (9.007)	22.920** (8.978)	23.079** (8.915)	22.946** (8.980)	22.978** (8.946)	22.734** (9.029)	22.724** (9.030)	22.830** (8.978)	22.831** (8.985)	22.874** (8.961)	22.816** (9.013)	22.899** (8.997)
Sales growth	-0.710 (0.565)	-0.703 (0.564)	-0.722 (0.564)	-0.744 (0.564)	-0.730 (0.563)	-0.727 (0.564)	-0.731 (0.562)	-0.731 (0.563)	-0.723 (0.565)	-0.718 (0.565)	-0.708 (0.566)	-0.718 (0.566)	-0.709 (0.566)
Momentum	-0.008** (0.004)												
Investment	-0.451* (0.266)	-0.450* (0.265)	-0.452* (0.265)	-0.456* (0.265)	-0.454* (0.265)	-0.454* (0.265)	-0.454* (0.265)	-0.454* (0.265)	-0.454* (0.264)	-0.453* (0.264)	-0.451* (0.263)	-0.452* (0.264)	-0.449* (0.264)
ROE	0.008* (0.005)												
Firms FE	Yes												
Time FE	Yes												
Firms Cluster	Yes												
R ²	0.355	0.355	0.355	0.355	0.355	0.355	0.355	0.355	0.355	0.355	0.355	0.355	0.355
Observations	14105	14105	14105	14105	14105	14105	14105	14105	14105	14105	14105	14105	14105

Significance levels are: * p < 0.10 ; ** p < 0.05 ; *** p < 0.01

Table C-4: Responses of stock returns to Climate laws - High period of Climate Awareness (Emissions Intensity)

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)	(13)
Emissions	1.493** (0.700)	1.500** (0.702)	1.451** (0.702)	1.403** (0.702)	1.431** (0.700)	1.433** (0.702)	1.470** (0.701)	1.468** (0.703)	1.429** (0.709)	1.428** (0.705)	1.431** (0.708)	1.449** (0.704)	1.432** (0.709)
High Concerns - Law Event × Emissions	0.159 (0.692)												
High Concerns - 1M Dummy × Emissions		0.149 (0.484)											
High Concerns - 2M Dummy × Emissions			-0.757* (0.449)										
High Concerns - 3M Dummy × Emissions				-1.142** (0.508)									
High Concerns - 4M Dummy × Emissions					-0.884* (0.533)								
High Concerns - 5M Dummy × Emissions						-0.650 (0.462)							
High Concerns - 6M Dummy × Emissions							-0.519 (0.427)						
High Concerns - 7M Dummy × Emissions								-0.440 (0.357)					
High Concerns - 8M Dummy × Emissions									-0.631 (0.386)				
High Concerns - 9M Dummy × Emissions										-0.608 (0.378)			
High Concerns - 10M Dummy × Emissions											-0.567 (0.357)		
High Concerns - 11M Dummy × Emissions												-0.474 (0.361)	
High Concerns - 12M Dummy × Emissions													-0.498 (0.368)
Size	3.897*** (0.341)	3.892*** (0.340)	3.909*** (0.341)	3.929*** (0.340)	3.914*** (0.340)	3.915*** (0.340)	3.893*** (0.339)	3.896*** (0.340)	3.912*** (0.340)	3.912*** (0.342)	3.910*** (0.341)	3.903*** (0.342)	3.914*** (0.343)
TobinQ	-1.560*** (0.421)	-1.562*** (0.420)	-1.552*** (0.421)	-1.544*** (0.421)	-1.554*** (0.422)	-1.551*** (0.420)	-1.562*** (0.420)	-1.560*** (0.420)	-1.551*** (0.420)	-1.551*** (0.420)	-1.551*** (0.419)	-1.556*** (0.419)	-1.553*** (0.419)
Debt	3.189** (1.390)	3.178** (1.391)	3.222** (1.398)	3.272** (1.404)	3.234** (1.400)	3.238** (1.400)	3.183** (1.395)	3.189** (1.397)	3.218** (1.403)	3.217** (1.402)	3.212** (1.401)	3.199** (1.400)	3.218** (1.401)
Book-to-market	3.091** (1.419)	3.086** (1.419)	3.107** (1.420)	3.126** (1.419)	3.106** (1.420)	3.118** (1.419)	3.081** (1.422)	3.085** (1.424)	3.124** (1.425)	3.128** (1.429)	3.129** (1.422)	3.109** (1.421)	3.128** (1.420)
PPE	1.259 (3.266)	1.257 (3.267)	1.284 (3.253)	1.309 (3.239)	1.306 (3.248)	1.290 (3.242)	1.298 (3.267)	1.292 (3.259)	1.282 (3.231)	1.277 (3.226)	1.274 (3.228)	1.277 (3.240)	1.260 (3.225)
R&D	25.138*** (8.054)	25.115*** (8.062)	25.209*** (8.059)	25.332*** (8.051)	25.282*** (8.059)	25.250*** (8.055)	25.146*** (8.073)	25.147*** (8.065)	25.206*** (8.054)	25.207*** (8.053)	25.195*** (8.051)	25.179*** (8.065)	25.199*** (8.054)
Sales growth	-0.731 (0.615)	-0.731 (0.615)	-0.735 (0.615)	-0.738 (0.614)	-0.739 (0.615)	-0.734 (0.617)	-0.744 (0.616)	-0.741 (0.617)	-0.724 (0.619)	-0.724 (0.619)	-0.724 (0.621)	-0.733 (0.620)	-0.728 (0.620)
Momentum	-0.008* (0.004)	-0.008* (0.004)	-0.007* (0.004)										
Investment	-0.447 (0.275)	-0.448 (0.276)	-0.443 (0.275)	-0.437 (0.274)	-0.443 (0.274)	-0.441 (0.274)	-0.450 (0.274)	-0.449 (0.276)	-0.441 (0.274)	-0.440 (0.274)	-0.440 (0.272)	-0.444 (0.273)	-0.438 (0.272)
ROE	0.007 (0.005)	0.007 (0.005)	0.007 (0.005)	0.008 (0.005)	0.008 (0.005)	0.008 (0.005)	0.007 (0.005)	0.007 (0.005)	0.008 (0.005)	0.008 (0.005)	0.008 (0.005)	0.008 (0.005)	0.008 (0.005)
Firms FE	Yes												
Time FE	Yes												
Firms Cluster	Yes												
R ²	0.354	0.354	0.354	0.354	0.354	0.354	0.354	0.354	0.354	0.354	0.354	0.354	0.354
Observations	14105	14105	14105	14105	14105	14105	14105	14105	14105	14105	14105	14105	14105

Significance levels are: * p < 0.10 ; ** p < 0.05 ; *** p < 0.01

D Robustness check

We consider emissions level (intensity) in [Figure D-1](#) and [Figure D-2](#) ([Figure D-3](#) and [Figure D-4](#)) corresponding to estimation results from our baseline equation in [subsection 4.2](#) in [Section 4](#). More specifically, we graphically represent the estimated coefficient β_2 with both 95% and 99% confidence intervals. The estimation results when we remove the winsorization of our carbon emissions indicators (both in level and intensity) at 2.5% can be found in [Table D-1](#) and [Table D-2](#).

Figure D-1: 95% Confidence interval (Emissions Level)

Note: The figure represents the estimated coefficient of β_2 from [Equation C-1](#) when considering emissions intensity. Note that each point in the figure represents the estimated coefficient corresponding to different specifications distinguished by the value of the considered climate law indicator on the x-axis.

Figure D-2: 99% Confidence interval (Emissions Level)

Note: The figure represents the estimated coefficient of β_2 with a 99% confidence interval from Equation 3 when considering emissions level. Note that each point in the figure represents the estimated coefficient corresponding to different specifications distinguished by the value of the considered climate law indicator on the x-axis.

Figure D-3: 95% Confidence interval (Emissions Intensity)

Note: The figure represents the estimated coefficient of β_2 with a 95% confidence interval from Equation 3 when considering emissions intensity. Note that each point in the figure represents the estimated coefficient corresponding to different specifications distinguished by the value of the considered climate law indicator on the x-axis.

Figure D-4: 99% Confidence interval (Emissions Intensity)

Note: The figure represents the estimated coefficient of β_2 with a 99% confidence interval from Equation 3 when considering emissions intensity. Note that each point in the figure represents the estimated coefficient corresponding to different specifications distinguished by the value of the considered climate law indicator on the x-axis.

Table D-1: Responses of stock returns to Climate laws with winsorization at 2.5% (Emissions Level)

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)	(13)
Emissions	-2.834*** (0.828)	-2.821*** (0.829)	-2.827*** (0.829)	-2.832*** (0.830)	-2.819*** (0.830)	-2.820*** (0.831)	-2.788*** (0.831)	-2.780*** (0.832)	-2.797*** (0.833)	-2.798*** (0.833)	-2.823*** (0.832)	-2.825*** (0.831)	-2.827*** (0.832)
Law Event × Emissions	-0.204 (0.207)												
1M Dummy × Emissions	-0.329** (0.161)												
2M Dummy × Emissions		-0.152 (0.138)											
3M Dummy × Emissions			-0.070 (0.150)										
4M Dummy × Emissions				-0.146 (0.128)									
5M Dummy × Emissions					-0.119 (0.137)								
6M Dummy × Emissions						-0.270* (0.140)							
7M Dummy × Emissions							-0.281** (0.129)						
8M Dummy × Emissions								-0.186 (0.129)					
9M Dummy × Emissions									-0.170 (0.124)				
10M Dummy × Emissions										-0.064 (0.119)			
11M Dummy × Emissions											-0.052 (0.128)		
12M Dummy × Emissions												-0.039 (0.132)	
Size	3.745*** (0.276)	3.730*** (0.276)	3.735*** (0.276)	3.741*** (0.277)	3.727*** (0.276)	3.728*** (0.278)	3.692*** (0.276)	3.685*** (0.277)	3.704*** (0.279)	3.706*** (0.280)	3.734*** (0.281)	3.736*** (0.280)	3.739*** (0.280)
Tobin Q	-1.774*** (0.364)	-1.777*** (0.364)	-1.775*** (0.364)	-1.775*** (0.364)	-1.778*** (0.365)	-1.779*** (0.364)	-1.789*** (0.365)	-1.794*** (0.365)	-1.789*** (0.365)	-1.790*** (0.364)	-1.780*** (0.364)	-1.779*** (0.363)	-1.778*** (0.363)
Debt	3.965*** (1.259)	3.939*** (1.256)	3.953*** (1.258)	3.964*** (1.261)	3.939*** (1.258)	3.942*** (1.260)	3.886*** (1.255)	3.878*** (1.254)	3.910*** (1.259)	3.912*** (1.257)	3.953*** (1.262)	3.956*** (1.264)	3.961*** (1.263)
Book-to-market	2.220** (1.121)	2.215** (1.120)	2.214** (1.120)	2.217** (1.121)	2.212** (1.121)	2.210** (1.121)	2.188* (1.123)	2.175* (1.124)	2.186* (1.124)	2.184* (1.125)	2.203* (1.123)	2.205* (1.122)	2.208* (1.123)
PPE	27.399*** (7.868)	27.262*** (7.884)	27.361*** (7.882)	27.420*** (7.874)	27.335*** (7.897)	27.349*** (7.887)	27.168*** (7.926)	27.149*** (7.945)	27.263*** (7.922)	27.294*** (7.927)	27.424*** (7.882)	27.439*** (7.880)	27.451*** (7.876)
Sales growth	-0.316 (0.537)	-0.305 (0.536)	-0.309 (0.536)	-0.309 (0.537)	-0.306 (0.535)	-0.309 (0.536)	-0.300 (0.533)	-0.303 (0.532)	-0.313 (0.534)	-0.317 (0.535)	-0.320 (0.536)	-0.320 (0.536)	-0.320 (0.536)
Momentum	-0.014*** (0.003)												
Investment	-0.350 (0.266)	-0.348 (0.265)	-0.350 (0.265)	-0.350 (0.266)	-0.349 (0.266)	-0.350 (0.266)	-0.348 (0.266)	-0.349 (0.267)	-0.350 (0.267)	-0.351 (0.268)	-0.352 (0.267)	-0.352 (0.267)	-0.352 (0.267)
ROE	0.012*** (0.004)												
Firms FE	Yes												
Time FE	Yes												
Firms Cluster	Yes												
R ²	0.364	0.364	0.364	0.364	0.364	0.364	0.364	0.364	0.364	0.364	0.364	0.364	0.364
Observations	17079	17079	17079	17079	17079	17079	17079	17079	17079	17079	17079	17079	17079

Significance levels are: * p < 0.10; ** p < 0.05; *** p < 0.01

Table D-2: Responses of stock returns to Climate laws with winsorization at 2.5% (Emissions Intensity)

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)	(13)
Emissions	0.748 (0.739)	0.777 (0.742)	0.769 (0.744)	0.759 (0.746)	0.776 (0.743)	0.788 (0.747)	0.828 (0.749)	0.830 (0.750)	0.812 (0.753)	0.812 (0.750)	0.795 (0.751)	0.796 (0.750)	0.794 (0.753)
Law Event × Emissions	-0.217 (0.289)												
1M Dummy × Emissions		-0.445* (0.242)											
2M Dummy × Emissions			-0.247 (0.198)										
3M Dummy × Emissions				-0.128 (0.216)									
4M Dummy × Emissions					-0.183 (0.181)								
5M Dummy × Emissions						-0.203 (0.195)							
6M Dummy × Emissions							-0.329 (0.203)						
7M Dummy × Emissions								-0.306 (0.186)					
8M Dummy × Emissions									-0.229 (0.185)				
9M Dummy × Emissions										-0.212 (0.189)			
10M Dummy × Emissions											-0.151 (0.173)		
11M Dummy × Emissions												-0.140 (0.181)	
12M Dummy × Emissions													-0.119 (0.190)
Size	3.366*** (0.285)	3.354*** (0.284)	3.356*** (0.285)	3.361*** (0.284)	3.354*** (0.284)	3.340*** (0.284)	3.332*** (0.282)	3.332*** (0.282)	3.340*** (0.283)	3.340*** (0.284)	3.348*** (0.284)	3.348*** (0.284)	3.350*** (0.284)
Tobin Q	-1.575*** (0.375)	-1.583*** (0.375)	-1.583*** (0.375)	-1.580*** (0.375)	-1.584*** (0.376)	-1.587*** (0.375)	-1.598*** (0.376)	-1.599*** (0.376)	-1.594*** (0.376)	-1.594*** (0.376)	-1.590*** (0.376)	-1.590*** (0.375)	-1.589*** (0.375)
Debt	3.055** (1.314)	3.026** (1.307)	3.031** (1.310)	3.042** (1.313)	3.026** (1.309)	3.015** (1.308)	2.978** (1.302)	2.980** (1.303)	2.999** (1.307)	2.999** (1.307)	3.014** (1.310)	3.014** (1.313)	3.018** (1.314)
Book-to-market	2.002* (1.180)	1.987* (1.178)	1.985* (1.178)	1.993* (1.179)	1.983* (1.180)	1.972* (1.179)	1.939 (1.182)	1.933 (1.182)	1.946 (1.185)	1.944 (1.188)	1.955 (1.184)	1.955* (1.183)	1.960* (1.184)
PPE	1.448 (3.039)	1.436 (3.033)	1.437 (3.031)	1.440 (3.031)	1.432 (3.030)	1.425 (3.026)	1.409 (3.025)	1.417 (3.028)	1.427 (3.030)	1.430 (3.034)	1.433 (3.035)	1.430 (3.035)	1.426 (3.035)
R&D	27.240*** (6.886)	27.124*** (6.873)	27.173*** (6.885)	27.216*** (6.887)	27.179*** (6.886)	27.153*** (6.883)	27.072*** (6.873)	27.084*** (6.879)	27.134*** (6.888)	27.159*** (6.892)	27.213*** (6.888)	27.225*** (6.890)	27.239*** (6.892)
Sales growth	-0.102 (0.605)	-0.097 (0.604)	-0.097 (0.604)	-0.098 (0.604)	-0.098 (0.604)	-0.099 (0.603)	-0.101 (0.602)	-0.103 (0.603)	-0.106 (0.604)	-0.107 (0.605)	-0.108 (0.606)	-0.107 (0.606)	-0.106 (0.606)
Momentum	-0.013*** (0.003)												
Investment	-0.362 (0.268)	-0.364 (0.268)	-0.364 (0.269)	-0.363 (0.269)	-0.365 (0.269)	-0.366 (0.269)	-0.372 (0.270)	-0.372 (0.271)	-0.370 (0.272)	-0.370 (0.271)	-0.369 (0.271)	-0.369 (0.271)	-0.368 (0.271)
ROE	0.011*** (0.004)												
Firms FE	Yes												
Time FE	Yes												
Firms Cluster	Yes												
R ²	0.362	0.362	0.362	0.362	0.362	0.362	0.362	0.362	0.362	0.362	0.362	0.362	0.362
Observations	17079	17079	17079	17079	17079	17079	17079	17079	17079	17079	17079	17079	17079

Significance levels are: * p < 0.10; ** p < 0.05; *** p < 0.01